

THE USE OF PERCUSSION INSTRUMENTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT
OF UZBEK MUSIC PERFORMANCE

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Abstract: This article describes the use of percussion instruments in the development of Uzbek music, the majestic path of music in the process of development. The old, extremely rich and beautiful traditions of Uzbek folk music are first of all given the concept of its unique local style.

Key words: status, method, instrument, music, traditional performance, music, art, percussion, drum, circle, ensemble.

Аннотация: В этой статье описывается использование ударных инструментов в развитии узбекской музыки, величественный путь музыки в процессе развития. Древние, чрезвычайно богатые и красивые традиции узбекской народной музыки, прежде всего, дают представление о её уникальном местном стиле.

Ключевые слова: статус, метод, инструмент, музыка, традиционное исполнение, музыка, искусство, перкуссия, барабан, кружок, ансамбль.

The fact that our Uzbek national music art, which has been preserved for thousands of years, has not lost its value, shows how deeply rooted it is in the treasure of our music. In addition, as a result of the serious attention given to our national music art by our government, this rare musical heritage, which has been polished for several centuries, has taken a strong place in our lifestyle and life today. The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on April 6, 2018 "On holding the international status art conference" also creates the ground for the further development and improvement of the Uzbek national music art, our statuses. In addition, the Maqom Ensemble named after Yunus Rajabi, the establishment of Maqom groups in the regions, the establishment of specialized Maqom schools and the Uzbek National Music Art Institute named after Yunus Rajabi create the ground for further strengthening and mastering of Maqom in our

country. For example, if we look at the performance of our national music, skillful young people are increasing even in the remote areas.

We know that the method is one of the main means of expression in status performance. At the same time, we found it permissible to dwell on the words of the instrument, in addition to clarifying the importance of percussion instruments in the performance of status. By the beginning of the 21st century, attention to percussion instruments increased, and the composition of ensembles was expanded, not limited to the circle of maqam performance, but also including tabla and drum instruments.

First of all, the method determines the rhythm of the statuses, whether they are performed in a restrained or moving tone and serves to create a spirit. How the method is performed prepares the listener for the theme of the piece. With this importance, percussion instruments have their unique place in performance.

The group of percussion instruments known since ancient times included drum, chindovul, hurdy-gurdy and circle. One of them is a circle - a percussion instrument with no clear pitch, common in Uzbek musical instruments. In the circle, the system of methods was called "bum", "bak", "bakka" by teachers from long ago. The circle was called "dapp" in Khorezm, "doiradast" in Bukhara, "chirmanda" in Ferghana, and "doira" in Samarkand. Percussion is important in the performance of the maqam, and there are instrumental sections. Shashmaqam consists of six maqams and is divided into two parts: Mushkilot, that is, instrumental section, and Nasr singing section. The Mushkilot section consists of Tasnif, Tarji, Gardun, Mukhammas and Sakil musical instruments. The parts of the instrument are added in the statuses with their proper names. These instrumental tracks of Shashmaqom are carefully and complexly created in terms of melodic structure, and they are distinguished by their special impact on people.

Nowadays, musical instruments with percussion such as trumpet, trumpet, drum and circle are used in holidays and cultural ceremonies. The best circle performers in our country are Rustam Boltaev, Talib Temirov, currently Quadratilla Samadov, Inomjon Dadaboev, Shukurjon Azimov, The Abduramz Azimovs have

been organizing their circle ensemble and presenting Uzbek national methods to our art-loving people. We cannot imagine any of our national music without a percussion group.

A drum is a percussion instrument. There are many types of drums. It is made of wood and ceramic. The top is covered with animal skin. Together with the double drum, trumpet and trumpet, it forms the Uzbek national ensemble. Nowadays, it is widely used in weddings and shows, and it is also used in status performance, which adds a special new tone. Tabla, another sibling of percussion instruments, is an Indian musical instrument. The performer plays the tabla in different ways by hitting it with fingers and palms. Tabla is performed as a soloist and as the main accompaniment in various classical ensembles. This instrument is popular with Uzbek national music with its special tone.

In conclusion, we can say that by the present time, we can see that the performers of status have become much younger in terms of age. From year to year, talented musicians are growing up among the youth, playing our national melodies on the world stage and receiving applause from the audience. We can also see such achievements in percussion instruments. Our national percussion instruments, which provide leading methods in the creation of true national tone, spirit, and content, will continue to interest world artists in the future.

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